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ANNUAL REPORT

OF THE

ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT

GWALIOR STATE

FOR

Samvat 1983, Year 1926-27.

913.543061

GWALIOR
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CONTENTS.

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PART I.

	PAGE.
I. Office Notes	10
II. Administrative Changes and Orders	2
III. Work at Headquarters	2
IV. Tours	3
V. Conservation	3-6
Bagh	3
Mandasaur	4
Ujjain	4
Chanderi	5
Narwar Fort	5
Gwalior Fort	5
Padhavli	5
Suhania...	5
VI. Annual Up-keep	6
VII. Exploration	7
(a) Excavations	7
(b) Listing	7
Ujjain	7
Bagh	7
Suhania...	7
VIII. Epigraphy	8
IX. Numismatics	8
X. Archæological Museum	10
XI. At Home	11
XII. Photographs and Drawings	11
XIII. Office Library	12
XIV. Income and Expenditure	12
XV. Concluding Remarks	12

PART II. 27321

1.	Appendix A	Tour Diary	13
2.	" B	Statement of Expenditure on Monuments Conserved.	16
3.	" C	Monuments Listed	17
4.	" D	Inscriptions Copied	19
5.	" E	Antiquities added to Archæological Museum	22
6.	" F	Photo Negatives	24
7.	" G	Drawings	29
8.	" H	Books	30
9.	" I	Income	32
10.	" J	Expenditure	33
11.	Illustrations	Plates i to vi.	

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~~8-3~~

CONTENTS

1	I	Introduction
2	II	General Principles
3	III	Excavation
4	IV	Excavation
5	V	Excavation
6	VI	Excavation
7	VII	Excavation
8	VIII	Excavation
9	IX	Excavation
10	X	Excavation
11	XI	Excavation
12	XII	Excavation
13	XIII	Excavation
14	XIV	Excavation
15	XV	Excavation
16	XVI	Excavation
17	XVII	Excavation
18	XVIII	Excavation
19	XIX	Excavation
20	XX	Excavation
21	XXI	Excavation
22	XXII	Excavation
23	XXIII	Excavation
24	XXIV	Excavation
25	XXV	Excavation
26	XXVI	Excavation
27	XXVII	Excavation
28	XXVIII	Excavation
29	XXIX	Excavation
30	XXX	Excavation
31	XXXI	Excavation
32	XXXII	Excavation
33	XXXIII	Excavation
34	XXXIV	Excavation
35	XXXV	Excavation
36	XXXVI	Excavation
37	XXXVII	Excavation
38	XXXVIII	Excavation
39	XXXIX	Excavation
40	XL	Excavation
41	XLI	Excavation
42	XLII	Excavation
43	XLIII	Excavation
44	XLIV	Excavation
45	XLV	Excavation
46	XLVI	Excavation
47	XLVII	Excavation
48	XLVIII	Excavation
49	XLIX	Excavation
50	L	Excavation

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PART II

1	A	Introduction
2	B	Excavation
3	C	Excavation
4	D	Excavation
5	E	Excavation
6	F	Excavation
7	G	Excavation
8	H	Excavation
9	I	Excavation
10	J	Excavation
11	K	Excavation
12	L	Excavation
13	M	Excavation
14	N	Excavation
15	O	Excavation
16	P	Excavation
17	Q	Excavation
18	R	Excavation
19	S	Excavation
20	T	Excavation
21	U	Excavation
22	V	Excavation
23	W	Excavation
24	X	Excavation
25	Y	Excavation
26	Z	Excavation

11/8/58

ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT
OF THE
DEPARTMENT OF ARCHÆOLOGY, GWALIOR STATE,
FOR THE
YEAR ENDING 30TH JUNE 1927, SAMVAT 1983.

PART I.

I. Office Notes.

1. *Charge.*—The undersigned held charge of the Department throughout the year of report.

2. *Leave.*—Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows:—

(a) Inspector : Privilege leave for twenty-one days.

(b) Photographer-draughtsman: Leave for four months and fourteen days consisting partly of privilege leave, partly of sick leave and partly of leave without pay.

(c) General assistant: Privilege leave for fourteen days.

(d) Officer correspondence: Privilege leave for seven days.

(e) Record-keeper: Leave for one month and sixteen days comprising privilege leave, sick leave and leave without pay.

3. *New Posts.*—To meet the requirements of the increasing work the following posts proposed last year were sanctioned and filled in the year of report:—

(a) Assistant photographer-draughtsman.—This post was given to V. M. Shavrikar, an inhabitant of this State. He is a young artist who has passed the intermediate examination in drawing and painting of the J. J. School of Art, Bombay, and has practised photography as well.

(b) Curator.—Sukhram Thakur, also an inhabitant of this State, was appointed to this post. He is an under-graduate, who was found in a test examination to be better equipped with the knowledge of Sanskrit and history than any other applicant for the said post.

4. *Promotions.*—(a) Superintendent: An increment of seventy-five Rupees has been sanctioned in the monthly salary of this post in the budget, out of which a promotion of Rupees twenty-five is to take effect from the beginning of the year under report.

(b) Inspector and (c) General assistant: An increment of Rupees twenty-five was sanctioned in the monthly salary of each of these posts in the budget, out of which a promotion of Rupees ten is to take effect from the beginning of the year under report.

II. Administrative Changes and Orders.

5. (a) An order was passed (*vide* Home Department letter No. 1688, dated 15-12-26) to the effect that the Superintendent of Archaeology was no longer one of the ex-officio secretaries of the portfolio.

(b) This Department was transferred from the Home Portfolio to the newly created Portfolio "Public Works" from the 1st of February 1927.

(c) The increasing office routine work left the Superintendent little time to attend to publication and other important work and necessitated an assistant to look after mundane office work. To achieve this end it was proposed to convert the post of overseer into that of Inspector, combining the duties of overseer and office assistant. The proposal having been approved, the designation of the existing overseer was changed into Inspector and the new responsibility was added to his duties as overseer.

(d) No circular with special reference to this Department was issued during the year of report.

(e) Publication of annual reports was sanctioned.

6. *General*.—All the office staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, diligently and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

III. Work at Headquarters.

7. In addition to the ordinary routine of office the following work was done during the Headquarters season:—

(a) The *Annual Administration Report* for Samvat 1982 was drawn up and submitted.

(b) A resume of the conservation and exploration work accomplished by the Department in the year 1925-26 was contributed to the *Annual Report* of the Archaeological Survey of India.

(c) Miscellaneous Notes on Bagh Caves were contributed to the *Monograph* on Bagh Caves, being published by the India Society of London, with the co-operation of this Department.

(d) New acquisitions of antiquities in the Museum were classified, arranged and labelled.

(e) The draft of *A Guide to Chanderi* was revised and made ready for the press.

(f) Arrangements were made with the G. I. P. Railway for putting up sign-boards at certain stations in this State to draw attention of passengers to archaeological monuments situated in their vicinity.

(g) Arrangements were made with the Superintendent of Archaeology, Bhopal State, for exhibiting at the travellers' Bungalow at Sanchi, photographs of the neighbouring important archaeological monuments situated at Beenagar and Udaygiri in this State.

(h) A set of enlarged photographs was supplied to the Gwalior Grand Hotel for exhibition with a view to attract travellers to visit our monuments.

(i) The collection of coins belonging to the State Museum was examined and catalogued.

- (j) An article on an Arabic-Persian inscription from Narwar was contributed to the *Indian Antiquary*.
- (k) An exhibition of select archaeological antiquities was organised in the Educational week celebrated in connection with the Madhav Jayanti.

IV. Tours.

8. During the year of report the Superintendent spent 151 days in camp.
9. A part of the tour consisted in trips outside the State for:—
- (a) Attending the fourth session of the All-India Oriental Conference held at Allahabad, in November 1926, as a delegate from the State Archaeological Department.
- (b) Interviewing the Director-General of Archaeology in India in February 1927 at Delhi in response to his call in connection with the publication of a book on Bagh Caves.
- (c) Interviewing our Offg. Political Member in camp at Bombay in connection with the proposal of the preservation of the Caves at Bagh.
10. The remaining portion of the tour was confined to the State territories being for directing and measuring the conservation works in progress, for the annual inspection of monuments already conserved, and for the exploration of fresh monuments. Thus all the conserved monuments at Gwalior, Narwar, Surwaya, Udaypur, Bhilsa, Udaygiri, Ujjain, Mandasaur and Bagh were inspected in the year of report. Narwar, Padhavli, Suhania and Bagh were visited on account of the conservation work going on there. Ujjain was visited partly for conservation and partly for exploration.
11. The detailed tour diary is given in Appendix A.

V. Conservation.

12. Conservation work was carried out at Bagh, Mandasaur, Sondni, Ujjain, Chanderi, Narwar, Gwalior, Padhavli and Suhania at a total cost of Rs. 10,723-4-3 including part of special grants for Narwar fort and Bagh caves.
13. The statement of monuments conserved in the year of report is set forth in Appendix B.
14. *Bagh*.—The clearance of the caves having been nearly completed, the work of repairing the decayed portions of walls and pillars and providing new supports to such portions of ceilings as were left overhanging by the disappearance or decay of original pillars was taken up and some progress made in Cave No. 2, last year. A special grant for further repairs to these caves was sanctioned this year by the Council of Regency. But the work was delayed partly on account of the late sanction to the grant and partly owing to a prolonged discussion on the proposed measures of preservation. The actual work that could be done here in the year of report consisted therefore only in the clearance of a few cells and in repairs to a part of facade of Cave No. 2 and in the collection of material for more extensive repairs to Cave No. 4, the most important of the series.

15. Some cells of Cave No. 2 are very dark and full of bats' dung, filthy dust and polluted air. Much difficulty was experienced in the attempt to clear these cells as no workman could work there for any considerable length of time with impunity. However the work was started last year and was proceeded with further in the year of report. This gave a clue to another adjacent cave which was hitherto not open to view, having completely collapsed and choked up with its own debris. The removal of debris though only partial has illuminated an obscure point. Hitherto it was believed that a series of cells one inside the other in the northern wing of Cave No. 2 was a secret passage leading up to the top of the hill. The clearance of debris shows that there is no such passage. The innermost cell abuts on the side of the next adjacent cave existence of which was so far unknown.

16. *Mandasaur*.—The monuments in the fort at Mandasaur and at Sondni which were conserved last year (*vide* Report for Samvat 1982) were further improved by providing descriptive notice boards giving a brief history of the monuments. The Sondni monument being of special interest, stone benches were provided in its compound for visitors' use. A coat of river sand was spread in the yard to make it look tidy. Trees were also planted at the corners of the compound but they did not thrive partly owing to the absence of a permanent care-taker on the site to look after them and partly owing to frost.

17. *Ujjain*.—Chaubis-Khamba gateway in the vicinity of Mahakala temple is one of the very few pre-Muhammadian monuments that have survived the ravages of time in this famous ancient city. It has been receiving attention of the Department for the last two years and the procedure of land acquisition having been completed this year, the conservation of the monument was taken up.

18. The following are the principal measures executed :—

- (a) The cracked lintels of the principal gateway and side galleries were supported on iron girders and rails.
- (b) The disturbed and decayed masonry on both the faces (northern and southern) was removed and replaced with good cut-stone masonry to match with the old work up to the roof level.
- (c) The roof was overladen with jungle, rubbish and debris. It was freed from these excrescences and a coat of good brick in lime concrete was laid over it to make it water-tight.
- (d) Modern *kacheha* houses had encroached within close proximity so as to block the view of the building. At the instance of the Archaeological Department these houses were acquired and cleared off by the Ujjain Municipality. The space thus opened all round the monument was levelled in stages and supported with retaining walls with a view to provide a sort of passage for the visitors, wishing to see the monument from all sides. The tops of platforms were again covered with stone in lime concrete to avoid damage by rain and to give a tidy appearance.

(e) The front face and a greater part of the sides of the gateway were freed from an obstinate coat of red lead with which these were covered. This sort of superfluous application of red lead is meaningless and detrimental to the clean appearance of this and other monuments in general and it is to be hoped that the worshippers would confine the application of red lead strictly to the two damaged images of *dwarapalas* now worshipped as goddesses.

19. *Chanderi*.—The monuments Koshak Mahal and Kati Ghati, which are already conserved were provided with descriptive inscriptions in Vernacular and English on or near them. These inscriptions are meant for helping visitors with brief historical and architectural notes on the respective monuments. It is intended to follow this course with regard to all conserved monuments of importance.

20. Chanderi is conspicuous in all the archaeological centres in the State for the wealth of old Muhammadar buildings which it possesses. Many of these monuments have been conserved by the Department. The next step towards their maintenance in good order all the year round was to appoint a permanent care-taker to look after them. This was done in the year of report.

21. It is a matter of regret that the Koshak Mahal was disfigured by the P. W. D. road gang who used it as temporary quarters. This is the second time that the P. W. D. subordinates are responsible for such vandalism to this valuable building. The matter has been brought to the notice of the A. O. Sahib, P. W. D., and it is hoped that he will see that his men will no more repeat acts of vandalism either at this or any other archaeological monument in the State.

22. *Narwar Fort*.—The small Roman Catholic church which was conserved last year was provided with a descriptive inscription giving its history in brief. The damage done by rain was also made good.

23. *Gwalior Fort*.—Some alterations and repairs were carried out at the Gujari Mahal in which the Archaeological Museum is located with a view to exhibit the fresco paintings from Bagh caves in a special room.

24. *Padhavli*.—Conservation work at the temple in the *garhi* at Padhavli made little progress in the year of report. Only some of the items already taken in hand were completed, while others were postponed as their execution was inter-related to that of certain other measures for which no sufficient funds were available in the year of report. A few trial trenches were also taken to find out the original ground level of the temple. This having been done, it will be now easy to take up further excavations round the monument so as to expose its basement to full view.

25. *Suhania*.—The big temple of Kakanmadh at Suhania was taken up for repairs last year (*vide Report for Samvat 1982*). As the work on this temple was started only about the close of the last year, it was executed mostly in the year of report. The items carried out comprise only a partial conservation of the monument. This was due partly to the paucity of funds and partly

to the fact that the procedure for the acquisition of the surrounding piece of land took time to complete. The following are the items executed:—

- (a) The jungle which grew on the temple and on the large mound on which the temple stands was cleared and rooted out.
- (b) The disturbed steps of the staircase leading up to the court-yard (the top of the lower platform) were reset.
- (c) A portion of heavy debris lying on the lower platform was taken down as a preliminary measure to find out the plan of the outer platform.
- (d) A few decorative sculptures on the basement of the temple which had moved out of their position were reset.
- (e) The staircase leading from the court-yard to the floor of the hall (*sabha mandapa*) which had been badly damaged was repaired by supplying the missing steps and resetting those that had been displaced.
- (f) The main temple was freed from its own heavy debris with which it was enveloped up to the top of its basement.
- (g) A few cracked lintels in the sanctum and the hall (*sabha mandapa*) were supported on iron girders and rails according to necessity.
- (h) The two decaying pillars were encased with cut-stone masonry up to their capitals, and the cracked but carved architrave which rested on these pillars was supported by inserting new lintels underneath it.
- (i) The two pillars of the hall which were leaning out were reset plumb.
- (j) The original doorway leading into the sanctum which was badly decayed had been repaired in later times by the insertion into it of an ugly modern door-frame. This latter was therefore taken away and the original door opening repaired with neat looking cut-stone masonry.
- (k) The damaged pilasters and cracked architraves in the interior of the sanctum were strengthened with cut-stone work.
- (l) Some dangerously hanging stones in the roof of the hall were either taken down or moved into a safe position.

VI. Annual Up-keep.

26. Annual clearance of jungle and petty repairs were carried out to all important groups of conserved monuments.

27. Nawab Sardar Sahibzada Sultan Ahmed Khan Sahib, Member for Appeals, and Major Hashmat Ullah Khan Sahib, Member for Public Works (both Members of the Council of Regency) inspected some of the archaeological monuments during their tours. The former paid a visit to monuments at Bagh, Mandasaur, Sondni, Chanderi and Narwar and the latter to Bagh caves only, and both were pleased to record a note of appreciation of the work, which this Department has been doing in the field of conservation.

VII. Exploration.

(a) Excavations.

28. No excavations were undertaken in the year under report. The excavations of a large mound at Pawaya which are lying unfinished will be resumed as soon as necessary funds are available.

(b) Listing.

29. *Ujjain*.—Exploration was this year practically confined to the extremely important site of ancient Ujjain. The political, commercial and above all cultural importance of Ujjain in the ancient history of India is too well-known to be dilated upon here. Suffice it to say that it is one of the most fascinating ancient sites in India for excavations which if successful are sure to illuminate many an obscure problem which has hitherto baffled solution. This is a huge and difficult task requiring careful study, extensive labour and abundant funds. But the results also are expected to be commensurately rich. The ancient site forms a long narrow band along the right bank of the river Sipra between the modern city and the village of Bhairongarh which lies two miles to the north. The site itself is popularly known as *garh* or fort as it is a tableland considerably higher than the surrounding ground and torn up by ravines.

30. As a modest beginning the survey of the surface indications was started in the year of report. But most of the monuments examined were found to be temples or shrines of modern origin and very few indeed of any archaeological interest. The site appears to have been badly disturbed. How much by the forces of nature and how much by the hand of man, it is difficult to surmise. Apparently a considerable share of the destruction goes to quarrymen who tampered with the ruins in search of material for the new town and to others who dug in search of petty treasures. The surface ground as it exists to-day is therefore singularly barren of antiquities. It will be only by sinking trial trenches that we shall be able to ascertain whether any ancient rains have survived intact and if so at what depth below the present ground level. This will therefore be the next step in the exploration of this interesting site.

31. Two interesting carvings were found built up in the embankment of the Rail-road (G.I.P.R.) near Ujjain. They are the upper and lower jaws of a huge water spout in the shape of the head of a crocodile (*makara*) with the mouth opened. The age of the sculpture is approximately the 10th century A. C.

32. *Bagh*.—An inscribed sculpture of Brahma was found on a crude platform in the town. For date and purport of inscription see under Epigraphy below.

33. *Suhania*.—Another very interesting sculpture was discovered at Suhania which abounds in ruins of mediæval monuments (*vide Report for Samvat 1982*). The sculpture is a representation of Vishnu in the *Visva-rupa* form possessing ten hands and five heads. It was picked up from inside the town and removed to Museum in the year of report.

VIII. Epigraphy.

34. Twenty-seven inscriptions as detailed in Appendix D were copied or noticed during the year of report most of which belong to Ujjain. The oldest of these come from Bhatnavar, a village in the Pohri Jagir of Sardar Bade Shitole Sahib. It was found (built in a platform) by Mr. Jugal Kishor, the then District Engineer, P. W. D., District Narwar, during his inspection tours. It has since been presented to Gwalior Archæological Museum by Sardar Shitole Sahib. The inscription is hopelessly worn out and hence undecipherable. However on palæographical grounds it may be assigned to about the 7th century A. C.

35. The next in importance is the inscription recorded on the pedestal of the image of Brahma discovered at Bagh. It is dated *Jyeshtha Vadi 13* V. S. 1210 and records the installation of the sculpture by Sri Bhamini, a sister of Sri Yasodhavala, a Paramara chief.

36. The remaining inscriptions are from Ujjain and with the exception of the two records on Bhartrihari cave which are dated in V. S. 1475 and 1493, all are modern, belonging to 18th and 19th century, badly damaged and undecipherable.

IX. Numismatics.

37. 55 gold, 556 silver, 604 copper, and 31 mixed metal or 1,246 coins in all were examined during the year of report. These were received in four lots.

38. The first lot of 1,111 coins belongs to the State Museum and has been sent to this office for examination and preparing a scientific catalogue.

The collection is composed as detailed below:—

(1) Out of forty-seven pieces of gold, nine are either medals or modern Indian or foreign coins. The remaining 38 coins which are of historical interest, cover a period from B. C. 300 to A. C. 1900 and represent the following varieties or dynasties:—

(i) Punch marked.

(ii) Kalachuris of Western Chedi.

(iii) Haihayas of Eastern Chedi.

(iv) Chandelas of Bundelkhand.

(v) Rathors of Kanauj.

(vi) Tomars of Ajmer and Delhi.

(vii) 1st dynasty of Vijayanagar.

(viii) 2nd dynasty of Vijayanagar

(ix) Gurkhali dynasty of Nepal.

(x) Early Sultans of Delhi.

(xi) The Mughal Emperors.

(2) Out of 496 silver pieces, 116 are modern European and Indian coins and 13 medals. The remaining 367 coins cover a period from B. C. 200 to A. C. 1900. The coins may be classified as

(i) Punch marked.

(ii) Western Kshatrapas,

(iii) Guptas.

(iv) Valabhis,

(v) Indo-Sessianian.

- (vi) Khichi Chohans.
- (vii) Gurkhali dynasty of Nepal.
- (viii) Early Sultans of Delhi.
- (ix) Sultans of Malwa.
- (x) Sultans of Gujrat.
- (xi) Mughal Emperors of Delhi
- (xii) Nawabs of Oudh.
- (xiii) Sikh rulers of the Punjab.
- (xiv) Rajas of Rajputana.
- (xv) Rajas of Central India.
- (xvi) Princes of Kathiawad.
- (xvii) Nizams of the Deccan.

(3) Out of the 509 copper pieces 2 are medals and 252 modern European, Colonial, and Indian coins. The remaining 255 coins are of some antiquarian interest, and cover a period from the 14th to 19th century A. C. They may be classified according to varieties or dynasties as under:—

- (i) Sessanian or Gadhiya.
- (ii) Sultans of Delhi.
- (iii) Sultans of Jaunpur.
- (iv) Sultans of Gujrat.
- (v) Sultans of Malwa.
- (vi) Bahmanis of Kulbarga.
- (vii) Mughal Emperors of Delhi.
- (viii) Chiefs of Rajputana.
- (ix) Chiefs of Central India.

(4) The remaining 14 pieces which are composed of mixed metal are medals belonging to Colonies.

39. The second lot consists of two silver coins only, received as specimens out of a treasure-trove find at Mandasaur. These are coined from a crude die of Shah Alam II but have no name, mint or date, and therefore are of no practical value.

40. The third lot is made up of 8 gold coins purchased from a coin dealer of Lucknow for the Archæological Museum. It comprises four Kushan coins, one of Kanishka, two of Huvishka and one of Vasudeva, and four Gupta coins, one of Samudragupta, two of Chandragupta II and one of Kumargupta.

41. The fourth lot of 125 pieces has in it 13 silver, 95 copper coins and 17 brass pieces. It was received from Babu Jugal Kishor, Special Engineer, P. W. D., at Ujjain. The lot consists mostly of cast and punch marked

coins often found at the site of old Ujjain during rains. Nearly all of them are in a bad state of preservation and may roughly be described as under:—

The silver coins are Western Kshatrapa and Indo-Sessianian or Gadhiya pieces. 12 copper coins belong to Sultans of Malwa and later Mughals and the rest are punch marked or cast coins too bad to decipher. The 17 brass tokens are mere pieces of brass plate cut round probably by some dealer to use them as weights or to pass them as coins.

42. Babu Jugal Kishore has kindly presented to our Archæological Museum 4 silver and 12 copper coins out of this collection for which the Department is very thankful to him.

X. Archaeological Museum.

43. Two stone inscriptions, five stone images, nine old miniature paintings in colour, eight gold, four silver, and twelve copper coins or in all forty antiquities were added to the Museum in the year under report (*vide* Appendix E). The inscriptions and sculptures come from Ujjain, Naderi, Bhatnavar and Suhania. Of these the inscription from Bhatnavar, a village in the Jagir Pohri, was brought to the notice of the Department by Mr. Jugal Kishore, the then District Engineer, P.W.D., District Narwar. It was secured as a present for the Museum from the Jagirdar Sahib, Sardar Bade Shitole, who deserves the thanks of the Department. The stone is very badly damaged and the record is all but completely obliterated.

44. The other inscription comes from a large *baodi* or step-well built in the 15th century at Naderi near Chanderi. The *baodi* is about to be submerged in an irrigation tank which is under construction and it was thought fit to rescue the record, though only of a secondary importance, from the impending watery grave.

45. The stone sculptures include a finely carved and well preserved image of the goddess Saraswati playing on the lute and a most interesting sculpture of Vishnu, both from Suhania (District Tonwarghar) and a nearly life size sculpture representing the *Tandava* dance of Siva from Ujjain.

46. The old miniature paintings were purchased from local dealers.

47. Of the coins eight gold pieces were purchased from a curio dealer of Lucknow and the rest have been received as a present from Babu Jugal Kishore, Special Engineer, P. W. D., at Ujjain, as already noticed under Numismatics.

48. To come to reforms introduced into the Museum in the year of report the first and the foremost is the appointment of a qualified curator whose main duty is to be a real guide to the visitors, *i. e.*, to help them with all reliable information which they may need regarding exhibits. For although most of the objects exhibited had already been furnished with labels giving their names, ages and find spots, many visitors were not quite satisfied with this much and made further inquiries with the illiterate care-taker who had been hitherto in charge of showing round the Museum. These he was naturally unable to answer. Thus a long-felt want which even found an expression in the written remarks of some of the visitors was supplied by the new arrangement.

49. Another reform worth mention is that the copies of the very interesting fresco paintings on the Buddhist caves at Bagh which were hitherto exhibited along with other objects in the main hall were transferred to a special room reserved for that purpose thus giving them the individual prominence which they deserved. This room was further furnished with large sized photographs of the Bagh caves. This little room thus affords an interested visitor the necessary facilities to study what is of importance from the viewpoint of art and architecture in that perhaps the most interesting group of ancient monuments in this State.

50. The third item of reform consists of the exhibition in the main hall, of large size in place of medium size photographs illustrating the more important of the ancient monuments in this State.

51. In the year of report 146 European and 409 Indian visitors have recorded their signature in the visit book kept at the Archæological Museum, though many more actually visited the institution. The visitors represent persons of almost all the cultured nations in the world of which the United State of America and England top the list. Most visitors have recorded their appreciation of the way in which the institution is being maintained.

52. The following were some of the distinguished visitors:—

Her Highness the Senior Maharani Sahiba, President of the Council of Regency, Gwalior, Her Highness the Begum Sahiba of Janjira and Her Highness' sister (Begum Atia Fyzee Rahman of Bombay), Sir Chintaman Rao Appasahib, the Chief of Sangli, the Rani Sahiba of Sangli, His Holiness Jagat Guru Shri Shankaracharya of Karvir Peth, Rai Bahadur Hira Lal of Jubbulpore, President of Nagari Pracharini Sabha, Benares, Mahamahopadhyaya Girdhar Sharma, Principal, Sanskrit College Jaipur, and R. S. Narayanswami, a distinguished disciple of Swami Ram Tirtha of blessed memory.

XI. At-Home.

53. For the last few years it was the practice of this Department to invite H. H. the Maharaja Sahib, the officers and the important gentry in the State to an annual At-Home with a view to bring them into touch with and to awaken their interest in the work of the Department. In view of the fact that these At-Home gatherings have already achieved their purpose fairly well and secondly in the interest of economy it was decided in the year of report to hold this gathering every third year instead of every year. No At-Home was therefore arranged in the year under report.

XII. Photographs and Drawings.

54. One hundred and thirty-six photographic negatives were prepared during the year of report as detailed in Appendix F. Besides fifty enlarged photographs of important and interesting monuments were prepared for being exhibited in the Archæological Museums at Gwalior and Sanchi and at the Grand Hotel at Gwalior. A good many photographic prints were made and supplied to the orders of the outside customers.

55. Nine drawings were made during the year of report as detailed in Appendix G.

XIII. Office Library.

56. Seventy-two books and journals on History, Art, Architecture and allied subjects were added to the Office Library in the year of report. Of these 55 were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments and Governments of Indian States, to whom our thanks are due. The list of books is given in Appendix H.

XIV. Income and Expenditure.

57. Statements of income and expenditure of the Department under different heads of the budget during the year of report are set forth in Appendices I and J, from which it will be seen that the annual expenditure was Rs. 29,090-5-8 including the part of the special grant sanctioned over and above the regular budget. The income was Rs. 446-15-0.

58. The recommendations made by the Home Member Sahib last year regarding the revision of the budget of the Department met with a favourable consideration of the Council of Regency. As a result the allotments to the various sub-heads of the budget were increased and the grant for repair and preservation of the ancient monuments was no longer confined to the very limited amount left in the fixed budget but the Department was advised to apply for non-recurring special grants according to necessity for the conservation of important monuments.

XV. Concluding Remarks.

59. In conclusion I am deeply grateful to Sir Appaji Rao Sahib Shitole, Amir-ul-Umra, Officiating Home Member, Shrimant Khase Sahib Pawar, Home Member, and Major Hashmat Ullah Khan Sahib, Member for Public Works, for the unfailing courtesy and valuable advice with which they continued to favour me in discharging the duties of this Department. I also beg to thank Sardar Sahibzada Sultan Ahmad Khan Sahib, Member for Appeals, and the late Lady Sultan Ahmad Khan Sahiba for the keen interest which they evinced in the work of the Department and for the earnestness with which they encouraged its activities.

M. B. GARDE,

Superintendent of Archæology,
Gwalior State.

PART II.

APPENDIX A

**Tour Diary of the Superintendent of Archaeology, Gwalior State
for the year 1926-27, Samvat 1983.**

Date month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
August 1926. 28th.	Gwalior to Rithora.	
29th.	Rithora to Padhavli.	
30th.	Padhavli to Gwalior <i>via</i> Rithora.	
November 1926. 4th.	Gwalior to Allahabad.	
5th to 8th.	Halt at Allahabad.	
8th to 9th.	Allahabad to Gwalior.	
19th.	Gwalior to Nonera.	
20th.	Nonera to Suhania.	
21st-22nd.	Halt at Suhania.	
23rd.	Suhania to Nonera.	
24th.	Nonera to Gwalior.	
26th.	Gwalior to Narwar <i>via</i> Satanwara.	
27th.	Halt at Narwar.	
28th.	Narwar to Surways <i>via</i> Shivpuri and back to Shivpuri.	
29th.	Shivpuri to Gwalior.	
December 1926. 5th-6th.	Gwalior to Bareth.	
"	Bareth to Udaypur.	
7th.	Udaypur to Bareth.	
"	Bareth to Bhilsa.	
8th.	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.	
"	Bhilsa to Ujjain.	
9th.	Halt at Ujjain.	
10th.	Ujjain to Mhow.	

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
December 1926. 11th.	Mhow to Sardarpore.	
12th.	Sardarpore to Bagh.	
13th.	Bagh to caves.	
14th-16th.	Halt at Bagh caves.	
17th.	Caves to Bagh.	
18th.	Bagh to Sardarpore.	
19th.	Sardarpore to Mhow.	
20th.	Mhow to Mandasaur.	
21st-22nd.	Mandasaur to Sondni and back.	
22nd.	Mandasaur to Gwalior.	
January 1927. 10th.	Gwalior to Morena.	
"	Morena to Badagaon.	
"	Badagaon to Suhania.	
11th.	Halt at Suhania.	
12th.	Suhania to Gwalior <i>via</i> Badagaon and Morena.	
February 1927 23rd-24th.	Gwalior to Delhi.	
24th-26th.	Halt at Delhi.	
27th.	Delhi to Gwalior.	
March 1927. 2nd-3rd.	Gwalior to Ujjain.	
4th-10th.	Halt at Ujjain.	
11th.	Ujjain to Mhow.	
12th.	Mhow to Bagh.	
"	Bagh to Bagh caves.	
13th-16th.	Halt at Bagh caves.	
17th.	Caves to Bagh.	
"	Bagh to Dhar.	
18th.	Dhar to Mhow.	

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
March 1927. 18th.	Mhow to Ujjain.	
19th-29th.	Halt at Ujjain.	
30th-31st.	Ujjain to Gwalior.	
April 1927. 11th.	Gwalior to Rithora.	
,	Rithora to Padhavli.	
12th.	Padhavli to Gwalior <i>via</i> Rithora.	
13th-14th.	Gwalior to Ujjain.	
15th.	Ujjain to Indore.	
16th-17th.	Halt at Indore.	
18th.	Indore to Ujjain.	
19th-20th.	Ujjain to Mandasaur.	
21st.	Mandasaur to Ujjain.	
22nd-30th.	Halt at Ujjain.	
May 1927. 1st-31st.	Halt at Ujjain.	
June 1927. 1st-13th.	Halt at Ujjain.	
14th-15th.	Ujjain to Bombay <i>via</i> Rutlam.	
16th.	Halt at Bombay.	
17th-20th.	On casual leave.	
21st-22nd.	Bombay to Ujjain.	
23rd-27th.	Halt at Ujjain.	
28th-29th.	Ujjain to Gwalior.	

STATEMENT OF MOVEMENTS CONSOLIDATED DURING THE YEAR 1927-28 PART I 1928

VIKRAM B

APPENDIX B.
Statement of Monuments Conserved during the Year 1926-27, Samvat 1983.

Serial No.	Place.	Name of monument.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.			AMOUNT SPENT			REMARKS.
			Current year.	Last year.	Total.	Current year.	Last year.	Total.	
1	Bagh	Bagh caves	Rs. a p. 20,000 0 0	Rs. a p. ...	Rs. a p. 20,000 0 0	Rs. a p. 2,280 0 0	Rs. a p. ...	Rs. a p. *2,280 0 0	
2	"	Buddhist caves	...	...	...	...	...	...	
3	Mandasaur...	Carriage of a Gupta sculpture in Mandasaur Fort.	305 0 0	13 3 6	318 3 6	305 0 0	12 8 0	317 8 0	
4	Khilchipura.	Shrawan Pillar	...	24 0 5	24 0 5	...	23 8 0	23 8 0	
5	Sondni	Jayastambh	279 0 0	46 10 6	325 10 6	275 8 6	38 6 6	313 15 0	
6	Chanderi	Katighati	...	85 1 0	85 1 0	...	82 0 0	82 0 0	
7	"	Madarsa	...	7 2 0	7 2 0	...	7 2 0	7 2 0	
8	Gwalior Fort.	Additions and alterations and fitting up of a separate room for Bagh frescoes	415 0 0	...	415 0 0	370 4 9	...	370 4 9	
9	Narwar	Fort	...	2,208 14 3	2,208 14 3	...	642 15 6	642 15 6	
10	"	Minor monuments	162 0 0	15 3 0	177 3 0	143 5 9	14 3 0	157 8 9	
11	Padhavli	Repairs to an old Temple at Gadhi Padhavli.	294 0 0	...	264 0 0	274 14 9	...	274 14 9	
12	"	"	499 0 0	...	499 0 0	105 1 0	...	105 1 0	
13	Subania	Kakanmadh Temple	499 0 0	2,403 8 0	2,902 8 0	392 15 6	2,352 3 3	2,745 2 9	
14	Ujjain	Chaubis Khamba	1,925 0 0	...	1,925 0 0	1,686 8 3	...	1,686 5 3	
15	"	Repairs to Chaubis Khamba	372 0 0	...	372 0 0	360 0 0	...	†360 0 0	
		Total	24,750 0 0	6,184 4 8	30,934 1 8	6,193 7 6	4,529 12 9	10,723 4 3	

*Special Grant.

†From Miscellaneous Head.

APPENDIX C.

Monuments Listed during the Year 1926-27, Samvat 1983.

No.	Locality.	Name of monument.	Class of ownership.	REMARKS.
		District Tonwarghar.		
1	Suhania.	An interesting sculpture of Vishnu.		
		District Narwar (Pohri Jagir).		
2	Bhatnawar.	A loose inscribed stone.		
		District Ujjain.		
3	Ujjain (modern).	Pushpadantesvar Mahadeva Temple.		
4	"	Seven old sculptures near above.		
5	"	Rupesvar Mahadeva Temple and the old sculpture near them.		
6	"	Chhatri of Ranoji Scindia.		
7	"	" Bhawanibai, wife of Ranoji Rao.		
8	"	" Anna Purnabai, " "		
9	"	" Chimabai, " "		
10	"	" Baijabai, " Daulat Rao.		
11	"	An old Mughal painting in Chhatri of Baijabai.		
12	"	A loose sculpture of a lion near Chhatri of Ranoji Rao.		
13	"	Two Chhatris having good carving work (unassigned).		
14	"	A sculpture of seated Siva near the above.		
15	Old Ujjain.	Chaturvyuha Mandir.		
16	"	Hanuman Temple known as Gadh-ke-Hanuman.		
17	"	Chitragupta Temple with an old step-well and tank in the compound.		
18	"	Group of Ram and Krishna temples in Ankapat.		
19	"	" of temples at Gomti Kund.		
20	"	Twenty old sculptures loose and stuck up in walls.		
21	"	A sculpture of Siva and Parvati on a mound 100 yards south of Ankapat mound.		

No.	Locality.	Name of monument.	Class of ownership.	REMARKS.
2	Bherongarh.	Temple of Kala Bhairava.		
23	"	The sculpture of (Kamala) Surya in the compound of above temple.		
24	"	A loose sculpture outside compound of above.		
25	"	Ukhresvar Mahadeva temple.		1
26	"	Twenty old sculptures stuck up in the walls of temples and Ghat.		2
27	"	Siddhawat Ghat.		
28	"	" Temple.		3
29	"	Loose sculpture near above.		3
30 48	"	Old Ghats along the Sipra river, with loose old sculptures scattered near them.		3
40	"	Tarakesvar Mahadeva Temple.		3
50	"	Chhatries of Scindia family.		3
District Amjhera.				
51	Bagh.	A sculpture of Brahma incised.		3

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1926-27, Samvat 1983.

Serial No.	Local No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	R E M A R K S .
1		Ujjain Ramghat.	District Ujjain. In the temple of Tarakesh- war Mahadeva.	6	Nagari.	Marathi.	Daulat Rao Scindia.	V. S. 1855 Saka 1720 = A. D. 1798.	Both of these inscriptions together complete the record. It refers to the construction of or repairs to temple and Pisacha- mochan Ghat by Bahuji Patel, Lakshman Patel, son of Jagtap and Raghujji Patel, at the cost of Rs. 4,232 during the reign of Daulat Rao Scindia.	
2		"	"	7	"	"	"			
3		"	On Chaurasi Avatara ...	10	"	"	...	...	Very badly damaged and is therefore undecipher- able.	
4		"	On Chaurasi Linga ...	4	"	Hindi.	...	V. S. 1859?	Names of various gods in a crude rhyme are written here such as:— श्री राम लक्ष्मण भवन्ति काम जना वसिष्ठ वेङ्कट धाम संमत् १८ [५] ९.	
5		"	On Jamunaji Devi ...	4	"	"	...	V. S. 1858.	Records the installation of the image of Yamuna by Mulchand, Sobha- ram, Govind Ram and Govardhana.	
6		"	In Chaubis Khamba on the foot of the southern wall.	1	"	"	...	...	Only the name of Chaubis Khamba is written here.	

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1926-27, Samvat 1983. — (concl'd.)

Serial No.	Local No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
7		Ujjain Ramghat.	In Chaubis Khamba on the foot of the southern wall	1	Nagari.	Hindi.	...	...	Only two letters which too are illegible.	Damaged.
8		"	On the eastern side	1	"	"	...	...	महादेव ४ is written here.	
9		Ujjain.	In Chaubis Khamba on the foot of the southern wall.	1	"	"	...	...	महा देव सा [स] नं. ३४ is written here.	
10		"	On the foot of a bracket on the East Bhartrihari Cave (ग्वा)	1	"	"	...	...	Uninterpretable	Badly written.
11		"	In Ganga Temple near Mangal Nath's Bungalow.	3	"	"	...	...	Illegible	"
12		Ujjain Ganga Ghat.	" Temple near Mangal Nath's Bungalow.	7	"	Sanskrit.	...	Monday jyeshthasudi 5 wednesday V. S. 1887 Saka 1752 = A. D. 1830.	Records the construction of the Ganga Ghat and installation of Sambhu Linga and an image of Uma (Parvati) by Ganesa, son of Mahadeva Kibe by the order of his mother Rukmini.	
13		"	On the Bhartrihari Cave...	3	"	Hindi.	..	V. S. 1475 = A. D. 1418.	Illegible.	
14		"	"	1	"	"	...	...	देव शृंग is only written here.	
15		"	On the Temple of Ankapat.	1	"	"	...	V. S.	Illegible.	
16		"	On an image in Rama Temple.	3	"	...	...	1 (?) 19.	Damaged and illegible.	
17		Kalka.	On Garh-ki-Sati	5	Old Nagari.	Hindi.	...	V. S. 165 (1) ?.	Matter is not clear as it is much damaged and illegible.	
18		Ankapat.	On a Sati Stone	15	"	"	Akbar.	Jethavadi 8 Tuesday V. S. 1651 = A. D. 1594.	Record is not clear. It refers to the reign of Akbar.	Very badly written.

APPENDIX D.
List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1926-27, Samvat 1983

Serial No.	Local No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King	Date.	P u r p o r t	R E M A R K S.
19		Siddhavat	On a stone on the Siddhavat.	4	"	"	...	1541	Sun and Moon are inscribed on it. The matter is illegible.	"
20		"	In Siddhavat Temple ...	9	"	"	...	...	Illegible.	"
21		"	Under the Vat (banyan).	5	Old Nagari.	Hindi.	...	Wednesday Vaisakha Sudi 7, V. S. 1881 = A. D. 1824.	Records the names of certain persons of Mahajan caste of Indore and devotees of Siddhanath, viz Jadavji Chhabildas, Dallabram Kevalram, Bhamarant Ram, Ambaram, Thakorelal and Kishanlal.	"
22		Ujjain	On a stone in a staircase...	5	Nagari.	"	...	...	Uttamchand and some other names are only read here.	The piece is broken.
23		"	"	4	"	"	...	...	Sri Raja Devi Singhji Deva, Surat Singhji Deva, Sri Raja Bhajan Singhji Deva, are mentioned here	
24		"	On the bank	9	"	...	Daulat Rao Scindia.	Wednesday Vaisakha Sudi 7, V. S. 1881, Saka 1776 = A. D. 1824	Records the installation of an image of Nilakantheswar and construction of Vinayak Ghat and Chhatra by Kishan Lal Mahajan of Indore during the reign of Daulat Rao Scindia.	
25		Bhairon-garh.	On a stone in the Bhairava Nath Temple.	6	"	Hindi.	...	...	Names of dieties such as Sri Maharaj Bhairuji, Gajadhar, Harji and Kashi Vish? wa Nathji are partially read.	

APPENDIX E.

List of Antiquities added to the Museum of Archaeology in Samvat 1983.

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Measurements.
Stone Sculptures and Inscriptions.			
1	Bhatnawar,	Sanskrit inscription... ..	2' 5" × 1' 10"
2	Naderi.	" "	2' 2" × 1' 6"
3	Suhania.	Image of Vishnu with ten arms ...	2' 11" × 1' 10"
4	"	Image of Saraswati... ..	1' 11" × 1' 7"
5	"	A portion of a doorway frame ...	2' 10" × 1' 10"
6	"	A sculpture of a woman standing and yawning.	2' 1" × 10' 9"
7	Ujjain.	Image of Siva Tandava	3' 6" × 2' 0"
Old Paintings.			
8	Gwalior (from a dealer).	Daulat Rao Scindia (?) Name of painter given as Imam Baksh and date as V. S. 1835.	11½" × 8½"
9	"	Radha and Krishna seated in a Hindola or swing supposed to represent Hindola Raga, as this name is written on it. It further bears in Urdu name of a painter Chitramen, resident of Shahjahanbad (Delhi).	1' × 8½"
10	"	Radha and Krishna standing near a tank with flutes in hand; name of painter Pir Muhammad is given in Urdu and date as V. S. 1852.	12½" × 9'
11	"	Bhairava with a garland of skulls round his neck is seated on a pedestal with two females and is supposed to represent Raga Bhairava.	...
12	"	A Chieftain seated beside an ottoman, has sword in hand and a necklace of jewels in his neck.	12¾" × 9½"
13	"	A Chief, name given in Hindi as Partapsimha. It also bears Jeth Sudi V. S. 1596 as the date of Partapsimha's birth and Phalgun Sudi V. S. 1653 as that of his death.	1' 6" × 1' ¾"
14	"	A Chief seated on a pedestal offering prayer. Sword kept aside. Partapsimha is written in Hindi.	11½ × 8½
15	"	A country eye doctor commonly known as <i>Satia</i> , operating on the eyes of a man.	10" × 8"

No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Measurements.
16	Gwalior (from a dealer).	A King riding on an elephant with attendants or guards—a sort of procession.	1'5½" × 1'1½"
Coins.			
17-18	Lucknow (from a dealer).	Kushan King Huvishka	Gold.
19	"	" " Kanishka	"
20	"	" " Vasudeva	"
21-22	"	Gupta King Chandragupta II... ..	"
23	"	" " Samudragupta	"
24	"	" " Kumargupta II	"
25-27	Ujjain (a private collection).	Punch marked Circa A. C. 100 to 300 A.C. ...	Silver.
28	"	Gadhiya type (Indo-Sessanian)	"/
29-40	"	Cast coins with different symbols Circa A. C. 300 to A. C. 500.	Copper.

APPENDIX F.

List of Photographs Taken during the Year 1926-27, Samvat 1983

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
District Amjhera.				
1	Bagh Caves.	Cave No. 4. Interior view showing the collapsed pillars, before conservation.	Half.	
2-6	"	" " " "	"	
7-8	"	" " " "	Quarter.	
9	Bagh Town.	Inscribed image of Brahma	"	
District Gird-Gwalior.				
10	Lashkar.	The memorial platform of Rani of Jhansi— General view from south-east.	Full.	
11	"	" " near view	"	
12	"	" " two images on the platform ...	Half.	
13	Gwalior Museum	Old painting, procession on camel ...	"	
14	"	" " on horse back	"	
15	"	" " king and queen	"	
16	"	" " another king	"	
17	"	" " a king of Tanjore?	"	
18	"	" " a discourse	"	
19	"	Image of Vishnu standing	Full.	
20	"	Image of Siva Tandava	"	
21	"	Image of Saraswati seated	Half.	
22	"	" " Balarama	"	
23	"	Two elephants	"	
24	"	Portion of a broken door-frame ...	"	
District Mandasaur.				
25	Mandasaur Fort.	Image of Siva after conservation, front view.	Full.	
26	"	" " " " side view.	Half.	
27	"	Sravan ki kawad (Torana pillar) ...	"	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
28	Gwalior Fort.	Sravan ki kawad (Torana pillar) another view.	Half.	
29	Sondni.	Yasodharman's pillars from south-west after conservation.	Full	
30	"	" " from south-east after conservation.	"	
31	"	Dwarapalas, front view	"	
District Tonwarghar.				
32-33	Rithora.	A Khadga and a Trisul on a stone pillar ...	Quarter.	
34	Suhania.	Kakanmadh Temple ...	"	
35	"	A group of Jaina Images ...	"	
District Ujjain.				
36	Sonkuchh.	Images of Siva Tandava (Brass), front view ...	Half.	
37	"	" " " buck "	"	
38	"	" Sutradhar (black stone) ...	Quarter.	
39	"	An inscription ...	"	
40	"	An old brass object ...	"	
41	Ujjain (old).	Siddhavata Ghat, general view ...	Full.	
42	"	" " Vishnu Image...	Half.	
43	"	Old carving on the side wall of Dharam-Sala at Siddhavata Ghat.	Full.	
44	"	Kaliadeh Mahal, general view from west ...	"	
45	"	" " Kund. ...	Half.	
46-48	"	Gadh (Old Mound), general view ...	Full.	
49	"	Rumi-ka-Maqbara ...	"	
50	"	Bhartrihari Cave from south-west ...	"	
51	"	" " north "	Half.	
52	"	" " interior courtyard ...	Full.	
53	"	" " another "	"	
54	"	Image of Kali in Bhartrihari Cave ...	Quarter.	
55	"	Pir Machhandar Nath-ki-Dargah...	"	
56	"	" " " side view ...	"	
57	"	Kalika Temple, general view of temple and boundary wall from south-west.	Full.	

No.	locality-	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
58	Ujjain.	Kalika Temple. interior	Full.	
59	"	Thalmal Ganesa	Half.	
60	"	Image of Vishnu in the compound wall of Kalika Temple.	Quarter.	
61	"	Temple of Chaturmukha	"	
62	"	Image of Chaturmukha, front view ...	Half.	
63	"	" " " side " ...	Quarter.	
64	"	" " " back " ...	"	
65	"	Some images near Chaturmukha Temple ...	Full.	
66	" town.	Gopala Mandir, general view	"	
67	" "	" " interior doorway ...	"	
68	" "	" " Shikhara ...	"	
69	" "	Images of Radha and Krishna	"	
70	" "	Bina Nim-ki Masjid, front view	"	
71	" "	Purani (old) Sarai	"	
72	" "	Some sculptures near Pushpadantesvar Mahadeva Temple.	"	
73	" "	Chaubis Khamba under repair	"	
74	" "	" " after repair, front view ...	"	
75	" "	" " " " back view ...	"	
76	" "	Traces of sculpture on the jambs of Chaubis Khamba gate. now worshipped as Devi.	"	
77	" "	Newly constructed steps near Chaubis Khamba gate.	Half.	
78	" "	" " " another view ...	"	
79	" "	Bird's-eye-view of Ujjain	Full.	
80	" "	" " " another	"	
81	" "	Ghats on the Sipra river near Ujjain ...	"	
82	" "	" " " another view ...	Half.	
83	" "	Image of Siva and Parvati	"	
84	" "	Chhatri of Maharani Baijabai from north-east.	Full.	
85	" "	Image of Parvati near Ramghat... ..	Quarter.	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
86	Ujjain town,	Image of Siva and Parvati Ramghat ...	Quarter	
87	" "	A sculptured slab " ...	"	
88	" "	Begam-ka-Maqbara from south-east ...	Full.	
89	" "	Ganga Ghat from west ...	"	
90	" "	Mangal Nath Ghat ...	"	
91	" "	Bhairava Nath Ghat, general view ...	"	
92	" "	" , Doorway (Nagar Khana) ...	"	
93-95	" "	Sculptures in the courtyard of Bhairava Nath	Quarter.	
96	" "	Ukharesvar Mahadeva, general view from south-east.	Full.	
97	" "	Sculpture in wall at Ukharesvar ...	"	
98	" "	Siva standing at Ukharesvar ...	Half.	
99	" "	A memorial slab on Cremation Ghat ...	"	
100	" "	Gomati Kund, general view ...	Full.	
101	" "	Nandi in a temple at Gomati Kund ...	Quarter.	
102	" "	Temples of Rama and Krishna ...	Full.	
103	" "	Image of Sesha Sayi Vishnu ...	Quarter.	
104	" "	Vishnu on Garuda near Mahakalesvar Kund.	"	
105	" "	Vishnu standing ...	"	
106	" "	A standing image in wall ...	"	
107	" "	Two images in wall ...	"	
108	" "	" " " in another wall ...	"	
109	" "	Sculpture near Bade Ganesa ...	"	
110	" "	A piece of a pillar in Harasiddhi courtyard ...	"	
111	" "	Seated Trimurti near Ankapat ...	"	
112	" "	Siva and Parvati " " ...	Half.	
113	" "	Siva Linga " " ...	Quarter.	
114	" "	Carved pieces in ditch ...	"	
115	Undasa.	A hillock near Undasa village about three miles from Ujjain.	"	
116	"	" " " another ...	"	
117	"	" " " another ...	"	

No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
Miscellaneous.				
118	Chanderi.	Inscription in a mosque near Mardan Lohar's house.	Full.	
119	"	Inscription, Tapa Baodi	"	
120	Udaypur.	Inscription in <i>Shahi</i> Mosque	"	
121	...	Map of country round Bhilsa	"	
122	...	Map of country round Bagh	...	
123	...	A proud Maiden	...	
124	...	Head of Krishna	...	
125	...	A bath	...	
126	...	Krishna as a cowherd	...	
127	...	A bride	...	
128	...	Ragini Sohni	...	
129	...	Ganga	...	
130	...	The dance of Siva	...	
131	...	Crying for the Moon	...	
132	...	Radha	...	
133	...	Radha's play	...	
134	...	Radha and Krishna	...	
135	...	A loyal husband	...	
136	...	Baz Bahadur and Rupamati	...	

APPENDIX G.

List of Drawings Made during the Year 1926-27, Samvat 1983.

No.	Place.	Description.	REMARKS.
1	Bagh.	Site plan for a proposed Rest-House near the caves ...	100' = 1"
2	"	Plan of the proposed Rest-House ...	6' = 1"
3	"	" of the out-houses of the proposed Rest House ...	"
4	"	" of the proposed quarters for the Chowkidars of... caves.	"
5	"	" of the proposed well near the caves ...	3' = 1"
6	Ujjain.	Plan of the Chaubis Khamba gateway ...	8' = 1"
7	"	Survey plan of a portion of the old site of Ujjain ...	300' = 1"
8	Miscellaneous.	Tracing from a drawing of the standard plan of a Dak Bungalow.	10' = 1"
9	"	Tracing from a drawing of the standard plan of a Dak Bungalow out-houses	"

APPENDIX H.

List of Books added to the Office Library of the Superintendent of Archaeology during 1926-27 Samvat, 1983.

S.No.	Titles.	REMARKS
Archæological Survey Reports and Memoirs, Etc.		
1	Annual Report of the Archæological Survey of Ceylon for 1924-25 ...	Presented.
2	Report of the Superintendent, Archæological Survey of Burma, for 1926.	"
3	Annual Report of the Mysore Archæological Department for 1925.	"
4	Memoir of the Archæological Survey of India No. 26 (Two statues of Pallava Kings and five Pallava inscriptions in a rock-temple at Mahabalipuram (by H.) Shastri.	"
5	Memoir. 28 (Bhasa and the authorship of the 13 Trivendrum plays by H. Shastri).	"
6	Memoir. 29 (Specimens of Calligraphy in the Delhi Museum of Archæology by Maulvi Zafar Hussan).	"
7	Memoir. 31 (The Indus Valley in the Vedic period by R. P. Chanda)	"
Art.		
8	Indian Art and Letters Vol. 11, No. 1 for 1926	Indian So. Pub- lication.
9	" " " " 2 "	"
10	" " " 1 " 1 1927	"
11	Studies in Indian Painting by C N. Mehta	Purchased.
12	Catalogue of the Indian Collection in the Museum of Fine Arts at Boston, Part V, by Dr. A. K. Coomarswamy.	"
13	The Music of India by H. P. Popley	"
Epigraphy.		
14	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XVIII, Part V	Presented.
15	" " " Part VI	"
16	A Collection of Prakrit and Sanskrit inscriptions of Bhavnagar State.	"
17	A Collection of Arabic and Persian inscriptions of Bhavnagar State ...	"
18	Annual Report of South Indian Epigraphy for the Year 1926 ...	"
Guides.		
19	A Guide to Bombay.	Purchased.
Histories.		
20	History of Rajputana, Vol. II, by Rao Bahadur G. S. Ojha ...	"

Serial No.	Titles.	Remarks.
21	History of Mediæval Hindu India, Vol. III (downfall of Hindu India) by Rao Bahadur C. V. Vaidya.	Purchased.
22	Mediæval Hindu India (Moghul conquest) by Ishwari Prasad ...	"
23	Sivaji Souvenir ...	"
24	Siva Sambhita ...	"
25-36	Indian Antiquary from June 1926 to May 1927 ...	"
37-40	Quarterly Journal of the Mythic Society, Vol. XVII, Nos. 1-4 ...	"
41	Centenary Supplement to the J. R. A. S. of G.B. and Ireland Oct. 24	"
42-53	Modern Review from July 1926 to June 1927 ...	"
54-55	Indian Historical Quarterly, Vol. II, Nos. 3 and 4 for the year 1926...	"
56	" " " Vo. III, No. 1, for the year 1927 ...	"
57	Indian Antiquary for the year 1909 ...	"
Literature.		
58	The Centre of Ancient Civilisation by H. D. Daunt ...	"
59	" " " by Satyadeva ...	"
60	Skanda Purana (Sanskrit Text) ...	"
61	Raghuvamsa , ...	"
62	Betel Pachchisi in Hindi ...	"
63	Simhasan Battisi , ...	"
64	Pilgrimage of Ujjaini in Brief in Hindi ...	"
65	Atha Avantikshetra Mahatmya , ...	"
66	Chaurasi Linga Mahatmya , ...	"
67	Mrichchhakatikam (Sanskrit Text) ...	"
68	A Constructive Survey of Upanishadic Philosophy by R.-D. Ranade,...	"
Miscellaneous.		
69	The <i>Times of India</i> Annual 1927 ...	"
State Publications.		
70	Birthday Number of the <i>Jayaji Pratap</i> for the Year 1926 ...	"
71	Selections of Darbar Orders for 1981 ...	Presented
72	The General Statistics of the Gwalior State for Samvat 1975 ...	"

APPENDIX I

Statement of Income realised in 1926-27, Samvat 1983.

No.	Heads.	Amount.	REMARKS.
		Rs. a. p.	
1	By sale of photo-prints ...	130 7 0	
2	" publications ...	106 15 9	
3	" stone sculptures ...	61 0 0	
4	" old coins ...	41 10 0	
5	" Tender forms ...	8 0 0	
6	Miscellaneous...	98 14 3	
	TOTAL ...	446 15 0	

APPENDIX J.

Statement of Expenditure incurred during 1926-27 Samvat 1983.

No.	Heads.	Amount current year.	Amount last year.	Total.
		Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.
1	Salaries ...	9,279 12 6	...	9,279 12 6
2	Travelling Allowances	2,791 0 0	...	2,791 0 0
3	Contingencies	1,435 9 11	22 8 0	1,458 1 11
4	Books ...	389 7 5	14 15 0	404 6 6
5	Museum...	1,867 11 9	72 0 0	1,939 11 9
6	Miscellaneous	432 0 0	150 11 3	582 11 3
7	Publication	509 15 6	...	509 15 6
8	Conservation Proper ...	4,763 11 3	4220 15 6	8,984 10 6
	Total ...	21,469 4 5	4,481 1 9	25,950 6 2
9	Expenditure over and above budget grant.	217 0 0	...	217 0 0
10	Special repairs to Bagh Caves ...	2,280 0 0	...	2,280 0 0
11	Special repairs to Narwar Fort ...	...	642 15 6	642 15 6
	GRAND TOTAL ...	23,966 4 5	5124 1 3	29,090 5 8

STATEMENT

of the Receipts and Disbursements of the

Date	Amount	Quantity	Description
1862	1000 00	1000 00	...
1863	2000 00	2000 00	...
1864	3000 00	3000 00	...
1865	4000 00	4000 00	...
1866	5000 00	5000 00	...
1867	6000 00	6000 00	...
1868	7000 00	7000 00	...
1869	8000 00	8000 00	...
1870	9000 00	9000 00	...
1871	10000 00	10000 00	...
1872	11000 00	11000 00	...
1873	12000 00	12000 00	...
1874	13000 00	13000 00	...
1875	14000 00	14000 00	...
1876	15000 00	15000 00	...
1877	16000 00	16000 00	...
1878	17000 00	17000 00	...
1879	18000 00	18000 00	...
1880	19000 00	19000 00	...
1881	20000 00	20000 00	...
1882	21000 00	21000 00	...
1883	22000 00	22000 00	...
1884	23000 00	23000 00	...
1885	24000 00	24000 00	...
1886	25000 00	25000 00	...
1887	26000 00	26000 00	...
1888	27000 00	27000 00	...
1889	28000 00	28000 00	...
1890	29000 00	29000 00	...
1891	30000 00	30000 00	...
1892	31000 00	31000 00	...
1893	32000 00	32000 00	...
1894	33000 00	33000 00	...
1895	34000 00	34000 00	...
1896	35000 00	35000 00	...
1897	36000 00	36000 00	...
1898	37000 00	37000 00	...
1899	38000 00	38000 00	...
1900	39000 00	39000 00	...
1901	40000 00	40000 00	...
1902	41000 00	41000 00	...
1903	42000 00	42000 00	...
1904	43000 00	43000 00	...
1905	44000 00	44000 00	...
1906	45000 00	45000 00	...
1907	46000 00	46000 00	...
1908	47000 00	47000 00	...
1909	48000 00	48000 00	...
1910	49000 00	49000 00	...
1911	50000 00	50000 00	...
1912	51000 00	51000 00	...
1913	52000 00	52000 00	...
1914	53000 00	53000 00	...
1915	54000 00	54000 00	...
1916	55000 00	55000 00	...
1917	56000 00	56000 00	...
1918	57000 00	57000 00	...
1919	58000 00	58000 00	...
1920	59000 00	59000 00	...
1921	60000 00	60000 00	...
1922	61000 00	61000 00	...
1923	62000 00	62000 00	...
1924	63000 00	63000 00	...
1925	64000 00	64000 00	...
1926	65000 00	65000 00	...
1927	66000 00	66000 00	...
1928	67000 00	67000 00	...
1929	68000 00	68000 00	...
1930	69000 00	69000 00	...
1931	70000 00	70000 00	...
1932	71000 00	71000 00	...
1933	72000 00	72000 00	...
1934	73000 00	73000 00	...
1935	74000 00	74000 00	...
1936	75000 00	75000 00	...
1937	76000 00	76000 00	...
1938	77000 00	77000 00	...
1939	78000 00	78000 00	...
1940	79000 00	79000 00	...
1941	80000 00	80000 00	...
1942	81000 00	81000 00	...
1943	82000 00	82000 00	...
1944	83000 00	83000 00	...
1945	84000 00	84000 00	...
1946	85000 00	85000 00	...
1947	86000 00	86000 00	...
1948	87000 00	87000 00	...
1949	88000 00	88000 00	...
1950	89000 00	89000 00	...
1951	90000 00	90000 00	...
1952	91000 00	91000 00	...
1953	92000 00	92000 00	...
1954	93000 00	93000 00	...
1955	94000 00	94000 00	...
1956	95000 00	95000 00	...
1957	96000 00	96000 00	...
1958	97000 00	97000 00	...
1959	98000 00	98000 00	...
1960	99000 00	99000 00	...
1961	100000 00	100000 00	...

(a) Yasodharman's Pillars at Sondni, view from north-east.

(b) Images of door-keepers (*dvarapalas*) at Sondni.

(b) Chauvis Khamba Gate at Ujjain, back view
after repairs.

(a) Chauvis Khamba Gate at Ujjain, front view
after repairs.

(b) Visvarupa (c) Vishnu, from Suhania.

(a) Siva dancing, from Ujiain.

(a) Balarama, from Indhar.

(b) Sarasvati, from Suhania.

(a) An old painting (a prince receiving instruction ?)

(b) An old painting (a cavalcade).

(a) An old painting (Rupamati and Baz Bahadur ?)

(b) An old painting (A Maratha king).

"A book that is shut is but a block"

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